

Left Hand Rule of Cross Product

Introduction

The generally accepted Cross product is based on the Right Hand Rule. Similarly an opposite version of Cross Product can be constructed by using Left Hand Rule for Cross Product.

Statement

Curl fingers of Left Hand from Vector A into Vector B and Thumb will point in the Direction of Cross Product.

Vector Equation

$$\mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B} = A B \sin\theta (\hat{n})$$

Octant Symmetry

There is an exact opposite octant for each octant of the 3D Cartesian Coordinate System, say this property of 3D Cartesian Coordinate System as octant symmetry.

Example: Third Octant has x and y negative and z positive and it has an opposite Octant with x and y positive and z negative (Fifth Octant).

Standard

Right Hand Rule of Cross Product and Left Hand Rule of Cross Product must be exactly opposite, which means there must be an Octant symmetry between Right Hand Rule of Cross Product and Left Hand Rule of Cross Product

Example: If the Right Hand Rule of Cross Product has the Third Octant that has x and y negative and z positive then Left Hand Rule of Cross Product must have an opposite octant with x and y positive and z negative (Fifth Octant).

Prove

In my Previous Research Paper named “**Faris’ Right and Left Hand Rule**” (Link is present at the end of this Research paper) ,I mentioned the Prove of Reference Line Direction for Faris’ Right and Left Hand Rule of Mechanics. There can be more Proves for this Reference Line Direction’s Second Condition.

Details

1. Left Hand Rule of Cross Product

There can be different orientations of Left Hand Rule of Cross Product. In total 6 orientations of Left Hand Rule of Cross Product exist because there are three positive and three negative directions in which the thumb can point. To define each orientation there are four octants in which two are possible these two are called “Orientation Standards” because two of the octants are equivalent to the other two. There are 6 Orientations of Left Hand Rule of Cross Product each with two orientation standards, so there are 12 left Hand Rule of Cross Product with respect to orientation standards.

Example: (1) Consider only one orientation of Left Hand Rule of Cross Product as:

Case 1: If +x axis is curled into +y axis

Case 2: if +y axis is curled into -x axis

Case 3: if -x axis is curled into -y axis

Case 4: if -y axis is curled into +x axis

(2) This orientation of Left hand rule of cross product is called fifth left hand rule of cross product because everytime result is -z axis, if result is -x axis its first, if +x axis its second, if -y axis its third, if +y axis its fourth, if -z axis its fifth and if +z axis its sixth.

(3) Case 1 and Case 3 are equivalent and Case 2 and Case 4 are also equivalent so only two octants are valid for each orientation of Left Hand Rule of cross Product.

(4) The last two cases (here Case 3 and Case 4) will become orientation standards of this orientation of Left Hand Rule of Cross Product. First orientation standard is called A Orientation Standard and second one as B orientation standard. The Octant Symmetry between Right Hand Rule of Cross Product and Left Hand Rule of Cross Product must be considered to decide which case is first (A Orientation Standard) and which is second (B Orientation Standard) for every orientation of left hand rule of cross product.

Fifth Left Hand Rule of Cross Product

The Fifth Orientation of the Left Hand Rule of Cross Product called Fifth Left Hand Rule of Cross Product (5th LCP) can be defined as:

Fifth Left Hand Rule of Cross Product's A Orientation Standard (5th LCP's A-OS): Curl fingers from -x axis into -y axis then thumb will show direction of -z axis.

Fifth Left Hand Rule of Cross Product's B Orientation Standard: Curl fingers from -y axis to +x axis and thumb will point in -z axis.

1. In Linear Mechanics

Reference Line Prove

I am given a cartesian coordinate system which include vectors \mathbf{n} (normal vector), \mathbf{r} (reference line vector) and $\mathbf{r}'(t)$ (position functions's n (th) time derivative quantity) and there negative vectors also. This is the cartesian coordinate system formed by plane including thumb and middle finger and the considered normal vector perpendicular to plane. In Faris' Right Hand Rule only Octant 1, Octant 4, Octant 5 and Octant 8 can be made by thumb, middle finger and normal vector. In Faris' Left Hand Rule only Octant 2, Octant 3, Octant 6 and Octant 7 can be made by thumb, middle finger and normal vector. These octants which include vectors are called initial octants and the cross product of vectors in each octant is like this $\mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{y}$, $\mathbf{y} \times \mathbf{z}$ and $\mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{x}$ the answer to these will give a resultant octant. I have to apply each orientation of Left Hand Rule of Cross product with its Orientation Standards to all Octants. $12 \text{ left hand rule of cross products with orientation standards} \times 8 \text{ octants} = 96 \text{ Cases}$.

For the prove of reference line direction's Second Condition (given below) I have applied Fifth Left Hand Rule of Cross Product's A Orientation standard to Octant 1 in Faris' Right Hand Rule and to Octant 7 in Faris' Left Hand Rule, note that both octants are opposite due to need of Octant Symmetry as a standard between Left and Right Hand. I have solved two cases below in this way.

1. Faris' Right Hand Rule

Octant 1 (On which 5th LCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{r}'(t) = -\mathbf{n} = -r r'(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

$$\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{n} = -\mathbf{r} = -n r'(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

$$\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{r} = -\mathbf{r}'(t) = -n r \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{i} \times \mathbf{j} &= -\mathbf{k} \\ \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{k} &= -\mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{i} &= -\mathbf{j} \end{aligned}$$

Combined

Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \cdot (\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{n}) = -|r|^2$$

Octant 1 (On which 6th LCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{r} &= \mathbf{n} = r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{r}^n(t) = nr \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{r}^n(t) &= \mathbf{r} = n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \end{aligned}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{k} \\ \mathbf{i} \times \mathbf{k} &= \mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{j} &= \mathbf{i} \end{aligned}$$

Combined

Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r}^n(t) \cdot (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) = |r^n(t)|^2$$

2. Faris' Left Hand Rule

Octant 7 (On which 5th LCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{r} \times -\mathbf{r}^n(t) &= -\mathbf{n} = -r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ -\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times -\mathbf{n} &= -\mathbf{r} = -n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ -\mathbf{n} \times -\mathbf{r} &= -\mathbf{r}^n(t) = -n r \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \end{aligned}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{i} \times -\mathbf{j} &= -\mathbf{k} \\ -\mathbf{j} \times -\mathbf{k} &= -\mathbf{i} \\ -\mathbf{k} \times -\mathbf{i} &= -\mathbf{j} \end{aligned}$$

Combined

Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \cdot (\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{n}) = -|r|^2$$

Octant 7 (On which 6th LCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times -\mathbf{r} &= \mathbf{n} = r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ -\mathbf{r} \times -\mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{r}^n(t) = nr \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \\ -\mathbf{n} \times -\mathbf{r}^n(t) &= \mathbf{r} = n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}} \end{aligned}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{j} \times -\mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{k} \\ -\mathbf{i} \times -\mathbf{k} &= \mathbf{j} \end{aligned}$$

$$-\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{j} = \mathbf{i}$$

Combined Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r}^n(\mathbf{t}) \cdot (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) = |r^n(t)|^2$$

Details

If one compares the proof of reference line direction's second condition in Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule, Octant Symmetry is seen. I have applied 5th LCP A-OS to Octant 1 and Octant 7 for Octant Symmetry between Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule. The scalar triple product equation is same because of Octant Symmetry and that is why the Octant symmetry is needed to not only make difference between Right and Left hand but also for same Scalar triple product. If the octant symmetry is not present and octants are same then scalar triple product cannot also make difference between right and left hand so Octant symmetry is important and in case of entirely different octants between right and left hand again making difference is impossible and also mathematically random.

2. In Angular Mechanics

Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule

In Clockwise and Anticlockwise movement, Faris' Right Hand Rule changes to Faris' Left Hand Rule and Faris' Left Hand Rule changes to Faris' Right Hand Rule respectively after 180 degrees of rotation or vibration. All octants are present in one rotation or vibration one can apply all 6 orientation of Left Hand Rule of Cross product with A and B Orientation Standard to all octants of one rotation and vibration.

Details

1. Types of Use

In the First Type of Use 3D cartesian coordinate system is divided among Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule. In Second Type of Use hand is shifted 180 degrees so that both hands can separately serve as a 3D Cartesian Coordinate system.

2. Visualizing all 96 Cases

Writing a simple equation of all 96 cases as

$$[\pm r, \pm r^n(t), \pm n] = \pm |N|^2 \quad \text{Where } |N| = |r| \text{ or } |r^n(t)| \text{ or } |n|$$

(1) I am given 8 octants for each of the six orientations of the left hand rule of cross product. The vectors in octant can be written as a Scalar triple product and then adding \pm with them is good to encounter all 8 octants.

(2) The factor still remains is to encounter only now 12 left hand rule of cross product in the equation so I notice in every left hand rule of cross product there is only arrangement difference of writing vectors in triple scalar product equation, sometimes ' $r^n(t)$ ' occurs first in the scalar triple product equation and sometimes ' n ' first so a simple scalar triple product equation that I mentioned can be changed by changing the vector's position.

(3) Now the two octant axes signs that are associated with each orientation of the left hand rule of the cross product does not matter because the actual cross product is between vectors and their signs in a given octant.

(4) For the two octants of each orientation of the left hand rule of cross product only resultant octant arrangement with all 8 given initial octants become different so only arrangement of initial resultant octant pairs becomes different for orientation standards of each left hand rule of cross product and for all six left hand rules of cross product only axes vectors cross products changes because sometimes there is $x \times y(r \times r^n(t)), y \times z(r^n(t) \times n)$ and $z \times x(n \times r)$ or $[r, r^n(t), n]$ and in any other left hand rule of cross product only cross product direction changes as $y \times x(r^n(t) \times r), x \times z(r \times n)$ and $z \times y(n \times r^n(t))$ or $[r^n(t), r, n]$.

3. Rules of Unit Vector

There is an Octant Symmetry between Right hand rule of cross product and Left hand rule of cross product as there is between Faris' Right hand rule of mechanics and Faris' Left hand rule of mechanics. The reason of Octant symmetry is to make difference between right and left because octant symmetry shows difference on the basis of positive and negative and scalar triple product equation is same otherwise if octant symmetry is not present and there is same octant then scalar triple product is also same and no way to make difference. In case there is entirely different octant (not same and no octant symmetry) then difference by octant comparison is not possible and scalar triple product equation is also mathematically random.

The proof of change of rules of unit vectors because of octant symmetry can be given but it is not present in Faris' right hand rule and left hand rule because of Hand Rule Sequence.

Hand Rule Sequence

1. Right hand rule of cross product and Left hand rule of cross product
2. Faris' Right and Left hand rule of mechanics

Explanation

Since the right and left hand rule of cross product are applied on the octants of Faris' Right and Left hand rule. Therefore cross product rules comes first and my rules afterwards any other rule any other person makes can list down in this sequence. There can be many initial resultant pairs because when anyone applies cross product rules on my hand rules initial octant and get a final octant one can again apply cross product rule on this final octant by considering it initial and get another set of initial resultant pair but the hand rule sequence remains same.

Comparison

$$A \times B = (y_1 z_2 - y_2 z_1) \mathbf{i} + (x_2 z_1 - x_1 z_2) \mathbf{j} + (x_1 y_2 - x_2 y_1) \mathbf{k}$$

$$A \times B = - [(y_2 z_1 - y_1 z_2) \mathbf{i} + (x_1 z_2 - x_2 z_1) \mathbf{j} + (x_2 y_1 - x_1 y_2) \mathbf{k}]$$

The first equation shows how to get the answer of cross product of two unit vectors A and B for right hand rule of cross product and the second shows how to get answer of two unit vectors A and B for left hand rule of cross product but do not include - sign of second equation in the resultant get by this equation i have just added it for mathematical stability otherwise for difference between right and left answers must be opposite. So indeed rules of unit vector invert.

4. Curl Direction

Sometimes it becomes very difficult to apply the Right and Left hand rule of cross product on octants due to extreme orientation of the hand in that direction.

Example

Suppose you are sitting on a chair and your desk is the xy plane now while applying 5th LCP's A-OS, hand is curled very much you can change the curl direction instead of curling -x to -y(resultant is -z) just curl -y to -x(resultant is +z) because curl direction are opposite to make them same by adjusting both curl direction to the curl direction of 5th LCP A-OS just add a "**Curl Direction Correction Sign**" in your resultant as -(+z) of your curling of -y to -x.

Note

In the octant symmetry of the right and left hand rule of cross product the curl direction is same which is another need of octant symmetry as a standard and the octant symmetry is actually between resultant vectors of final or resultant octant.

Conclusion

First I stated the Left hand rule of cross product then I added octant symmetry as a standard between Right and left hand rule of cross product. I have applied the Left hand rule of cross product on Divided Octant Use of Faris' Right and Left hand rule of mechanics and solved two cases, the Combined Octant Use of my hand rules is equivalent. At last all 96 cases are visualized and the reason for inverting of rules of unit vector is told. A small thing called curl direction correction is introduced.